

Electrochemical studies on textile dye naphthol yellow S with particular reference to colour removal

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Aromatic nitro dyes are resistant to chemical and biological oxidation and to hydrolysis because of electron withdrawing nitro groups. Consequently they are environmentally persistent and remediation of waste streams and contaminated water is difficult. In the present work, the electrochemical study has been carried out on the nitro acid dye naphthol yellow S predominantly used in textile dyeing. On the basis of results of the electrochemical study experimental conditions are optimized for the controlled potential electrolysis of the model dye. Complete decolourisation resulted after 1 to 3 h of controlled potential electrolysis. Kinetics of decolourisation was monitored and half-life period determined. Chromatographic study revealed formation of single decomposition product and COD decreased substantially in the decolourised solution.

Nitro aromatics comprise an important class of potential environmental contaminants as a result of their wide use as textile dyes, agrochemicals and other classes of industrial chemicals. Most of them are highly toxic even at low concentrations¹. Nitro aromatics in the form of colourants have been identified in surface, drinking, rain, sea and groundwater². Aromatic nitro dyes are resistant to chemical and biological oxidation and to hydrolysis because of the electron withdrawing nitro groups. Consequently they are environmentally persistent and remediation of waste streams and contaminated water is difficult³.

The increase in hazardous chemical pollution together with awareness of its long term consequences have reinforced the need for developing sensitive, selective and effective technique for monitoring and treatment of these nitro aromatic dyes present as effluents in environment. In the present work, electrochemical study has been carried out on the nitro acid dye naphthol yellow S predominantly used in textile dyeing. The results of the electrochemical study are assessed in terms of decolourisation and reduction in toxicity.

2,4-Dinitro-1-naphthol-7-sulphonic acid (A)

Naphthol yellow S (A) is known commercially by the trade name of Ext. D & C Yellow No. 7 and it is certified by

FDA for colouring drugs and cosmetics intended for external applicants. It is used in the form of sodium and potassium salt for dyeing wool and silk in an acid bath, giving pure yellow shades⁴.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetry :

The cyclic voltammetric studies of naphthol yellow S were carried out at platinum and glassy carbon working electrodes in the varying pH range and at varying scan rates and concentrations. Cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 1) of the dye molecule showed two cathodic peaks in forward scan. Out of these two peaks, the peak at lower potential had been assigned to the reduction of nitro group at second position in naphthol ring and the other at higher potential was attributed to reduction of nitro group at fourth position of the naphthol ring. This assignment has been done on the basis of experiments done in this laboratory⁵. The difference between anodic peak potential ($E_{p,a}$) and cathodic peak potential ($E_{p,c}$) was usually more than 60 mV suggesting irreversible nature of the electrode process⁶. With increasing concentration of naphthol yellow S, peak potential shifted towards more negative potential indicating difficulty in reduction. The plot of $i_{p,c}$ versus concentration is a straight line which supports the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process⁷. Similarly with the increase in scan rate, the cathodic peak potential ($E_{p,c}$) showed negative shift in both the reduction peaks (Table 1) while the anodic peak potential was found to shift towards positive

direction. The irreversible nature of the electrode process is further supported by shift of i_p with v and the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process is supported by the linear plot of i_p (peak current) versus $v^{1/2}$ (v = scan rate) passing through the origin (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of naphthol yellow S (2×10^{-4} M in distilled water) at platinum working electrode at varying scan rates (mV/s) : (1) 100, (2) 200, (3) 500, (4) 1000, (5) 1500, (6) 2000.

Fig. 2. Plot of $i_{p,c}$ vs $v^{1/2}$ of naphthol yellow S in distilled water at platinum foil working electrode, conc. 2×10^{-4} M.

Studies at various pH :

Cyclic voltammetric studies of naphthol yellow S in the pH range (3.3–12.0) and at varying scan rates (100 to 1000 mV/s) exhibited two well-defined reduction peaks after pH 5.0 at both platinum and glassy carbon electrodes. These two reduction peaks merged with the background current at alkaline pH (7.4–9.2). From pH 10.5 to 12.0 again a prom-

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of naphthol yellow S (2×10^{-4} M in distilled water) at platinum working electrode, scan rate 200 mV/s : (1) before electrochemical treatment. (2) after electrochemical treatment.

inent cathodic peak appeared. Anodic peak ($E_{p,a}$) is showing constant negative shift with increase in pH (Table 2). Almost linear negative shift in cathodic peak potential is observed upto pH 6.0 after which there is little change in $E_{p,c}$ with pH and constancy is seen in the peak potential up to pH 8.8. The shift of $E_{p,c}$ with increasing pH indicated the proton participation during electro reduction⁸. After pH 6.0 reduction of unprotonated species take place as equilibrium shifted towards unprotonated form.

Table I. Cyclic voltammetric characteristics of naphthol yellow S (2×10^{-4} M) at various scan rates at (1) pH 3.3, (2) in distilled water, (3) at pH 7.4

Sl. no.	pH	Scan rate (mV/s)	\sqrt{v}	$-E_{p,cI}$ (V)	$-E_{p,cII}$ (V)	$-i_{p,cI}$ (μA)	$-i_{p,cII}$ (μA)	$-E_{p,aI}$ (V)	$i_{p,aII}$ (μA)
1.	3.3	100	10.0	0.594	0.808	263.4	173.1	0.384	128.2
2.		200	14.14	0.651	0.865	348.8	226.8	0.253	194.5
3.		500	22.36	0.676	0.957	500.0	304.8	0.171	305.1
4.		1000	31.62	0.712	0.957	604.9	368.3	0.118	390.5
1.	Distilled water	100	10.0	0.345	0.858	40.09	-	0.833	97.68
2.		200	14.14	0.367	0.858	74.00	-	0.811	111.1
3.		500	22.36	0.438	0.907	92.06	-	0.769	123.3
4.		1000	31.62	0.476	0.918	101.05	-	0.776	128.2
5.		2000	44.72	0.456	0.923	-125.6	-	0.747	133.1
1.	7.4	100	10.0	0.217	0.961	8.394	103.5	0.701	72.93
2.		200	14.14	0.271	0.996	12.46	106.0	0.651	77.81
3.		500	22.36	0.317	-	18.97	-	0.609	118.5
4.		1000	31.62	0.416	-	40.99	-	0.587	157.5
5.		2000	44.72	0.633	-	63.35	-	0.559	184.3

Controlled potential electrolysis :

Controlled potential electrolysis (at -1.20 V) of naphthol yellow S solution (2×10^{-4} M) in distilled water employing platinum foil and steel foil as working electrodes resulted in complete disappearance of colour indicating the reduction of chromophoric nitro group. With Pt foil as working electrode, the peak current becomes almost negligible leading to decolourisation of the coloured solution within 3 h of cpe (Fig. 3) while with steel foil as working electrode the complete decolourisation of initial coloured solution took 1.30 h. The anodic peak current is also reduced considerably. The data pertaining to controlled potential electrolysis of dye at different electrodes are presented in Table 3. Similar results were obtained on cpe of dye solution at different pH (5.0–7.4) whereas at pH 5.0 complete disappearance of cathodic peak was observed. While in the pH range 8.2–10.3 one additional cathodic peak at less negative potential is obtained after cpe. This may be due to the formation of some electroactive product. Voltammetric characteristics at varying pH are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Voltammetric characteristics of naphthol yellow S (2×10^{-4} M) at various pH at platinum foil working electrode, scan rate = 200 mV/s

pH	$-i_{p,c}$ (μ A)	$-E_{p,c}$ (V)	$-i_{p,a}$ (μ A)	$E_{p,a}$ (V)		
3.3	348.8	0.865	194.5	0.253		
4.0	250.8	0.907	171.9	0.452		
5.0	185.3	0.904	139.2	0.452		
6.0	$i_{p,cI}$ 135.3	$i_{p,cII}$ 267.0	$E_{p,cI}$ 0.804	$E_{p,cII}$ 0.980	136.7	0.552
7.4	$i_{p,cI}$ 12.46	$i_{p,cII}$ 106.0	$E_{p,cI}$ 0.271	$E_{p,cII}$ 0.996	104.0	0.651
8.2	$i_{p,cI}$ 18.81	$i_{p,cII}$ 159.7	$E_{p,cI}$ 0.203	$E_{p,cII}$ 1.070	132.1	0.669
9.2	105.00	1.01	126.9	0.644		
10.3	–	1.02	107.1	0.797		
11.2	43.0	1.02	179.8	0.836		

Coulometric studies :

The value of n , number of electrons involved in the reduction of naphthol yellow S at different pH (above 5.0) and aqueous neutral medium and at platinum and steel electrodes were found to be 8.0 ± 0.2 .

Chromatographic studies :

After controlled potential electrolysis of the coloured dye solution, TLC studies were carried out on decolourised/electrolysed solution of naphthol yellow S dye to qualitatively know the number of end products of cpe. It was observed that the electrolysed solution exhibited a single broad band in acetone-water (8 : 2) pointing towards the formation of a single product.

Table 3. Voltammetric characteristics of naphthol yellow S (2×10^{-4} M) before and after electrochemical treatment at different working electrodes

$v = 200$ mV/s

Working electrode used	Before [A] after [B] electro-chemical treatment	$-E_{p,c}$ (V)	$-i_{p,c}$ (mA)	$-E_{p,a}$ (V)	$-i_{p,a}$ (μ A)
Platinum foil	A	0.367	0.858	16.91	85.81
	B	–	–	–	–
Steel foil	A	0.367	0.858	16.91	85.81
	B	–	–	0.772	52.84

Spectral studies :

The UV-visible spectra of 2×10^{-4} M naphthol yellow S dye solution at varying pH (3.3 to 11.2) was recorded in the region 300–600 nm. Naphthol yellow S solution exhibited two well-defined absorption bands at 395 nm and 430 nm. Controlled potential electrolysis in aqueous neutral medium was carried out at -1.20 V by employing both steel foil and platinum foil as working electrodes. The progress of electrolysis was monitored by recording spectral changes at different time intervals. Peak at 395 nm and 430 nm decreased with time and after around 1–2 h of cpe completely colourless solution was obtained with both Pt foil and steel foil indicating reduction of chromophoric nitro group. Decrease in absorbance was faster in case of platinum electrode as compared to steel electrode.

The plots of time vs $\log A_t$ (at 430 nm) were linear, indicating that the disappearance of colour followed first order rate kinetics both with steel and platinum foil working electrode. Rate constants for electrochemical reduction of naphthol yellow S dye on platinum foil and steel foil working electrode are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Rate constants for electrochemical reduction of naphthol yellow S on platinum foil and steel foil working electrodes

Compound	Working electrode used	Initial applied vs SCE (V)	Conc. (M)	K_{obs}/min^{-1}	$t^{1/2}$ Half life period (min)	R_{obs}
Naphthol yellow S	Platinum foil	-1.20	2×10^{-4}	3.14×10^{-2}	22.07	6.28×10^{-6}
	Steel foil	-1.20	2×10^{-4}	2.5×10^{-2}	27.72	5.0×10^{-6}

Chemical oxidation demand :

In comparison to initial COD concentration of coloured dye solution, the COD value of treated/decoloured solution shows 65% decrease from 2560 mg/L to 920 mg/L indicating considerable decrease in toxicity.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out on a

BAS CV-27 Cyclic Voltammograph in connection with a Digital electronic 2000 Omnigraph x-y/t recorder. Conventional three-electrode system was used in which electrodes were dipped directly in the solution to be electrolysed. For controlled potential electrolysis, platinum foil ($3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$) and steel foil ($4.5 \times 3.5 \text{ cm}^2$) were used as working electrode, SCE as reference and platinum wire as auxiliary electrode. Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out using EG and G Potentiostat of Princeton Applied Research Model VersaStat II integrated with Applied Electrochemistry Software. pH metric measurements were made on Hach EC-40 bench top pH/ISE meter. The kinetics was studied using Elico SL 159 UV-visible spectrophotometer for absorbance measurement.

Chemical oxidation demand (COD) was determined by the open reflux method using COD digester from Spectra lab (2015-S). Pre-coated TLC plate was obtained from E. Merck.

Procedure :

For the purpose of cyclic voltammetric measurements solution of naphthol yellow S were prepared by taking 1 ml stock solution of the dye, +8.0 mL of appropriate BR buffer/distilled water and 1 mL of 1.0 M KCl (supporting electrolyte). Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out at different pH, varying scan rates and different concentrations of depolariser. The results thus obtained provide optimum conditions for the reduction of dye. Controlled potential electrolysis of the dye solution was carried out at -1.20 V . Progress of electrolysis was monitored by recording cyclic voltammograms at regular intervals. Coulometer was used to read the quantity of current directly and n was calculated by $Q = nFN$, where N represents the total number of moles of the dye initially present. Absorbance of the solution at λ_{max} 430 nm is recorded at different time intervals during electrolysis. Absorbance kinetics is monitored and

observed first order rate constants for reactions and half-life period ($t^{1/2}$) of end product are then determined. The end product of electrolysis was determined by chromatographic method.

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References

1. E. A. Patty, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", Interscience, New York, 1963; I. M. Kolthoff, P. J. Elving and F. H. Stross, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Part III, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1971, 2, 125; A. Pala and E. Torat, *Water Research*, 2002, **36**, 2920.
2. P. M. Berster and J. Bersier, *Trends in Anal. Chem.*, 1986, **5**, 141; J. Bell, J. J. Plumb, C. A. Buckley and D. C. Stuckey, *J. Environ. Eng.*, 2000, **126**, 1026; M. Hable, C. Stern, C. Asowat and K. Williams, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.*, 1991, **29**, 131; A. Hashimoto, H. Sakino, E. Yamagami and S. Tateishi, *Analyst*, 1980, **105**, 787; A. Hashimoto, H. Kozima, H. Sakino and T. Akiyama, *Water Research*, 1979, **13**, 509; T. F. Jenkins, P. H. Miyares, K. F. Myers, E. F. McCormick and A. B. Strong, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1994, **69**, 289.
3. C. Achitnich, E. Fernandes, J. M. Bollag, H. J. Knackmuss and H. Lenke, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1999, **33**, 4448.
4. K. M. Shah, "Handbook of Synthetic Dyes and Pigments", Synthetic Dyes II ed. Multichem, Mumbai, 1998.
5. Rajeev Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 308.
6. L. Meites, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publications, New York, 1967.
7. T. Kissinger and R. Heineman, "Laboratory Techniques in Electro-analytical Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1984.
8. G. G. Aylward, J. L. Garnett and J. H. Sharp, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **39**, 457; J. L. Sadler and A. J. Bard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **90**, 132; I. M. Issa, R. M. Issa, Y. M. Termerk and M. R. Makwond, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, **18**, 139.